

Review

Exploring Learning Poverty as a Component of Quality Education in Primary Schools of Rwanda: A Critical Analysis

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Abstract: The issue of learning poverty, which signifies the inability of students to attain essential literacy and numeracy skills, has gained significant prominence in the global education landscape. This research undertakes a comprehensive examination of learning poverty as a crucial facet of quality education, with a specific focus on the primary school system in Rwanda. Through a thorough analysis encompassing historical perspectives, current realities, and prospective trajectories that have materialized with the pursuit of education for all, this study endeavors to shed light on the intricate elements that contribute to the prevalence of learning poverty in Rwandan primary schools. By critically assessing the effectiveness of existing educational practices and interventions, this research seeks to untangle the multifaceted factors that underlie the manifestation of learning poverty in this context. The analysis reveals that the notable increase in primary school enrollment over the past 15 years has not only raised concerns about the quality of education but has also resulted in the emergence of learning poverty as a consequential outcome. This study finds that learning poverty is primarily attributed to the discrepancy between the growing enrollment and the limited availability of learning infrastructure, tools, materials, and qualified teaching staff. Therefore, it is suggested to establish a transformative education strategy that revolves around early, strategic, and inclusive investments, prioritizing foundational skills and quality outcomes.

Keywords: Primary school, learning poverty, education for all, Rwanda, enrollment, education

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Introduction

Article 26 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UNESCO, 1948) clearly states that education is a basic, fundamental human right. In the declaration, the following was stated “everyone has the right to *education*”. According to UNESCO, it is stipulated that education should be provided without charge, particularly at the primary

and foundational levels. Compulsory elementary education is imperative. The provision of technical and professional education should be universally accessible, while higher education should be equally attainable by all individuals based on their merit. The entitlement to education encompasses not solely the opportunity to obtain education, but also the entitlement to acquire education of commendable caliber. [1].

Quality education can have many meanings [2]. In Rwanda, it is considered when “all children leaving school equipped with the skills, knowledge, attitudes and values needed for Rwanda’s economic and social development and for their own further educational and social development” [3]. Literacy and numeracy are recognized as vital skills that enable young to participate as equals in a growing knowledge and technology-based economy.

Quality education goes beyond literacy and numeracy. It is not measured simply by the teachers’ knowledge-imparting ability or by the student’s test scores. It has to do with the moulding of human beings into well-rounded, well-adjusted and constantly developing members of society. It denotes the capacity to acquire and develop the knowledge that is critical to each individual’s growth and evolution, as well as to his/her role as a productive member of society.

Quality education ought to prepare the learner for, and enable him/ her to adapt to, rapid technological change. The workplace of today differs greatly from that of the past. Similarly, the workplace of tomorrow will be radically different from that of today. The skills required to work on an assembly line will be grossly inadequate in an information economy that relies on artificial intelligence as well as human intelligence. Unfortunately, the movement towards quality education has been impeded by a serious learning crisis that has been developing for many years before the massive disruption inflicted by the COVID-19 pandemic [4].

Cecchi (1998) defined poorly educated persons as those “who do not acquire a minimum educational threshold needed to survive”, the minimum being represented by the completion of compulsory schooling as it is stipulated by each school system. According to Cecchi, educational poverty can be understood as a dual form of deprivation. The first aspect pertains to an individual’s deficiency in “functional abilities” necessary for engaging in various social and economic endeavours. The term “other” pertains to the incapacity of an individual with limited education to generate a financial income within the labour market. The younger generations are particularly impacted. [5].

The current global learning crisis carries significant implications for the future. Despite notable advancements in facilitating children’s access to education in recent years, the diligently achieved entitlement to education has not been effectively transformed, for a considerable number of individuals, into a more advantageous entitlement to acquire knowledge. As per the World Bank’s report, a staggering 90% of children in low-income countries are unable to comprehend reading material by the time they reach the age of ten. The issue of ensuring that education effectively facilitates learning is of great concern for numerous states, particularly those located in sub-Saharan Africa where Rwanda is located. This phenomenon in question exerts a significant influence on the well-being of individuals and their livelihoods, as well as on the overall economic growth and development of entire nations. [4].

Children living in the Sub-Saharan African region have historically experienced the most severe levels of learning poverty, a condition characterized by limited access to quality education and inadequate learning outcomes. However, it is important to note that other regions also exhibited significant levels of learning poverty prior to the onset of the pandemic. In the year 2019, the learning poverty rate in Africa stood at 86 per cent, while it exceeded 50per cent in three additional regions, namely the Middle East and North Africa with a rate of 63per cent, South Asia with a rate of 6per cent, and Latin America and the Caribbean with a rate of 5per cent.

Regrettably, advancements in addressing the issue of learning poverty had come to a halt even prior to the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic. There was a notable improvement observed before 2015, as the global prevalence of learning poverty experienced a decline from 61 per cent to 53per cent during the period spanning from 2000 to 2015. In light of this context, there has been a rise in the prevalence of learning poverty from 53per cent in 2015 to 5per cent in 2019. The repeated regional assessments conducted in 2019 for Sub-Saharan Africa and Latin America revealed minimal or

negligible progress. The region of Sub-Saharan Africa continues to exhibit the highest prevalence of learning poverty, with population growth in this area playing a significant role in the escalation of the global learning poverty rate [6]. Many countries are lagging in terms of learning since they are suffering from learning poverty. According to World Bank (2019), the concept refers to the lack of the ability to read and comprehend a simple text among fourth-grade students who are supposed to be 10 years old and about 56% of 10 years old children suffer the learning poverty. “Without urgent action, this generation of students may never achieve their full capabilities and earnings potential, and countries will lose essential human capital to sustain long-term economic growth, [7].

The PISA (Programme for International Student Assessment) results released by the OECD in 2018 indicate that over ten million students in participating countries were unable to complete even the most basic reading tasks. What is intriguing about this finding is that the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) countries are, unlike their ‘least-developed’ or ‘developing’ counterparts, neither economically nor technologically disadvantaged. It is bad enough when education fails to produce truly literate individuals. It is disheartening if it stops short of equipping school leavers with the skills they need to adapt to the demands of a rapidly changing world. It is an unmitigated disaster if education is unable to fulfil contemporary employment requirements.

Gains in access have also turned attention to the challenge of improving the quality of education and accelerating learning. Learning levels that have been measured in many developing countries are alarmingly low, especially among disadvantaged populations. Of course, even in poor learning environments, most students acquire some skills from school; but too often these skills are rudimentary at best. In some countries, recent studies show that a quarter to a half of youth who have graduated from primary school cannot read a single sentence [8].

Problem statement

Rwanda has achieved significant success in education and has reached universal access to primary education with a net enrolment rate of 98 per cent, hence partially progressing towards SDG 4 and the realization of articles 28 and 29 of the Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC). However, these gains at the primary level need to be matched with improvements in quality throughout the system. The 2016 move towards a competency-based curriculum was a major achievement; however, approximately half of the students are not acquiring foundational knowledge during primary school, with lower rates for rural children. The 2018 “Learning Achievement in Rwandan Schools” indicates gaps in learning outcomes, with significant issues in numeracy and literacy for most students, especially girls [9].

Rwandan education's overarching goal is to educate its people into skilled human capital for the nation's social and economic growth (MINEDUC, 2010). However, there is still no solution to the problem of producing vast cohorts of primary and secondary school graduates who lack a fundamental set of skills and a working knowledge of English [10]. After all, the pre-determined educational outcomes in Rwanda remain largely absent [11].

According to World Bank (2018), the human capital ranking in Rwanda scored 358/625, where 300 is the lowest point which indicates the learning outcomes for the human capital places Rwanda in the worst quartile. This statistic shows that Rwandan individuals' ability to contribute to productivity as future workers is still developing. Concerning the Human Capital Index (HCI), Rwanda has a score of 0.36/1, the fact showing that Rwandan residents' combined knowledge, skills, and health level is far below what is necessary for them to function as productive members of both the society and the wider world. Hence, it is important to issue a warning to Rwanda, urging it to put out even more effort into all of these HCI initiatives, particularly in education, given that maintaining national competitiveness in the global economy [12].

This learning poverty is demolishing a country's efforts for development, and threatening the world's human capital. Technology is already changing the nature of jobs in the world, jobs that no longer require low-skilled workers, but demand creative and collaborative soft skills. Artificial intelligence is already taken over many jobs that low-educated people used to depend on for a living. Thus, equipping schools for learning is a priority that can no longer wait. The goal now is providing learning for all, an aim that won't come true unless we galvanized our effort and build it on the quality of learning instead of merely desiring access.

The teaching philosophy places significant importance on both cognition and action as fundamental aspects of the learning process, regardless of whether one is engaged in experiential, conceptual, analytical, or practical learning. Metacognition holds significant value in all learning settings. This involves engaging in introspection and contemplating one's actions, reflecting on the underlying principles being explored, and evaluating how specialized knowledge is being implemented. It is not just about knowing and understanding [13]. This shows how education in some situations is not serving its purpose. Learning poverty, as the World Bank named it, is a crisis that is threatening countries' pains on building a life of dignity to people through quality education. Sustainable Development Goal 4 will not be realized unless the problem of learning is undertaken.

The concept of return investment in education developed by James Heckman known as the Heckman Curve demonstrated that the highest economic returns are seen in preschool programs, especially for disadvantaged cohorts, with returns gradually declining through post-school job training [14].

Other researchers [15] have identified these results, which indicate that early-age interventions are especially difficult to get right because there is less immediate and clear-cut feedback regarding the probable long-term economic consequences. The authors endorse an analysis that excludes programs with negative outcomes and studies with outlier returns. Using this methodology, the authors identify slightly higher average cost-benefit ratios for children ages 5 to 15 than for children ages 0 to 4 or older, thereby supporting the principle of primary age investments.

Research for the World Bank similarly identifies higher returns to primary age years of education than secondary age years of education [16], reinforcing earlier findings from Boissier (2004) regarding the significance of literacy and numeracy in general and the significance of investments in primary age education in particular. This reinforces the value of ensuring quality education at the primary level.

Figure 1. Heckman curve

According to the human capital approach, education is regarded as an investment that increases ‘the stock of skills and productive knowledge embodied in people’ (Rosen, 1989). The acquisition of education, synonymous with ‘investment in human capital’, increases the productivity of people, which converts into higher earnings. In turn, workers earn less because they are less productive, being deficient in human capital [5].

Policymakers and academic debate have centered on increasing the quantity of education, as measured, for instance, by mean years of schooling. While expanding access to education is important, the main objective of providing education is to impart knowledge and skills to students in the classroom[17].

Review of the past

As of the 2000s, most developing countries have been struggling to achieve universal enrolment in primary education for boys and girls to meet Millennium Development Goal. Rwanda has the great strides in improving enrolment/access indicators. Rwanda’s gross primary enrolment figures increased from 99.9% in 2001 to 110.2 % in 2003. This was considerably higher than the Sub-Saharan average of 75% [18]. This accomplishment can directly be attributed to the government’s new policy of free 9 years of basic education that was introduced and constitutes an important achievement in the fight against poverty [19]. As stated in its Vision 2020 policy document, the government aimed to transform Rwanda’s agricultural-based economy into a knowledge-based economy, for which human resource development is of vital importance [20].

The aggregate increases in enrolment after the elimination of fees reflect both increases in school attendance among the primary school-age population and Adult Education (MINEDUC, 2014), the introduction of fee-free and compulsory nine years of basic education 9YBE in 2009 and its extension to free and compulsory Twelve Years Basic Education 12YBE in 2012 [4].

For example, the primary completion rate for the 1998 – 2003 cohort was only 38.1%; the repetition rate was 20.6% and the dropout rate was 15.2%, the issue of quality is a major challenge [19]. The quality of primary education in Rwanda

is affected by a shortage of qualified teachers, classrooms, a heavy curriculum and a lack of appropriate instructional material. Indeed, the continued shortage of teachers has led to large classes and a double-shift system. However, there have been tremendous efforts to increase the number of qualified teachers. Nationwide, the proportion of qualified teachers has increased from 81.2% in 2002 to 85.2 % in 2003. While the overall teacher/pupil ratio is 65.8, the qualified teacher/pupil ratio reduced from 72.7 in 2002 to 70.3 in 2003, however, this ratio is still higher than what is required to ensure quality teaching. [19].

The 2014 Learning Achievement in Rwandan Schools (LARS) study assessed learning against the country's curriculum standards and found that P3 students averaged 54 per cent and 59 per cent on their tests for literacy (in Kinyarwanda) and mathematics respectively; for P6, the scores averaged 43 per cent and 44 per cent on literacy (in English) and mathematics respectively [21].

The following table shows how the quality-based factors have continuously been affected by massive student enrollment in primary schools, therefore, leading to educational poverty.

Year	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019
Total number of primary school students	1,857,841	2,019,991	2,150,430	2,190,270	2,264,672	2,299,326	2,341,146	2,394,674	2,402,164	2,399,439	2,450,705	2,546,263	2,540,374	2,503,705	2,512,465
Schools	2,295	2,323	2,370	2,432	2,469	2,510	2,543	2,594	2,650	2,711	2,752	2,842	2,877	2,909	2,961
Classrooms	29,748	30,434	30,737	30,989	31,453	27,184	28,817	28,914	29,367	30,011	30,477	31,437	31,927	32,548	34,468
Pupil classroom ratio	62	66	70	71	72	85	81	83	82	80	80	81	80	77	73
Pupil-teacher ratio	64	66	69	61	64	63	58	59	60	58	58	58	58	56	57
Pupil-teacher qualified ratio	74	73	75	73	73	69	63	62	63	61	62	62	59	57	58

Source: Rwanda statistical yearbook 2020

The presented table depicts the information regarding the lack of synchronicity between the progress in students' enrollment facilitated by the Education for All program and other quality factors, including the construction of numerous classrooms and the recruitment of qualified teachers, as a means of ensuring both access and quality education.

A. Statistical data on the increase in students' enrollment, schools and classrooms

Figure 2. Total number of students

This table shows that in 2005 and 2006, the total number of students in primary school was 1,857,841 and 2,019,991 respectively [suggesting the average increase of 60,040 students every year]. The tables suggest that the increase lasted till 2013 which could be attributed to the higher rate of repetition that prompted students to drop out. The table also shows that since 2015, when the government started sensitizing the community, the number of student enrolments has increased and sometimes decreased. This could be attributed to the fact that students have not been viewing education as important. In general, in fourteen years, the number of students increased by 654,624; this indicates a substantial increase in student enrollment.

Figure 3. Increase in the number of schools and classrooms

The presented figure represents the increase in schools and classrooms. Since the beginning the number of classrooms was increased to 31,453 in 2009, suggesting an increase of 1705 (5.73%) since 2005. The primary school classroom decrease in 2010 was linked to the need for many classrooms since the establishment of 9 years of Basic Education as some of the classrooms were used to serve that particular purpose. Thereafter government made an effort to build new classrooms but the gap continue up until 2017 to reach several primary classrooms that were in 2009.

There has been a significant surge in student enrollment, which has not been proportionately balanced with the availability of classrooms. Specifically, classrooms per enrolled students were 1:62.45 in 2005, 1:72 in 2009, 1:81.79 in 2013, and 1:79.56 in 2017. This imbalance has adversely impacted the quality of education, as the number of pupils in a class has exceeded the optimal level for effective teaching and monitoring by teachers. This has resulted in learning poverty in primary schools.

B. Rwanda education statistics of students per teaching staff ratio in Primary schools

Figure 4. Pupil ratios

According to statistical data presented in figure 3, primary schools are facing the issue of overcrowded classrooms, with an average of 73 pupils per class. This has resulted in a significant number of pupils, with a ratio of 59 pupils per teacher in the year 2019. As a result, a significant number of students experience difficulties in acquiring fundamental literacy and numeracy skills during their primary education, ultimately impeding their ability to pursue higher education and make meaningful contributions to national development.

According to [22] children learn better and teachers are more effective in smaller classes. Unfortunately, it has become almost impossible for the teacher to render individual pupil attention due to the big class size. Consequently, students’ academic achievement and performance are lowered. In these classes, the management of problems reduces teachers’ time, the intended content is not completed, and learners’ time to concentrate and complete a given task is reduced (Kelly, 1999). Indeed, overcrowded classrooms have a great impact on students’ involvement in learning [23].

C. OECD statistics of students per teaching staff in Early childhood education / Primary / Secondary, Ratio, 2020

Figure 5. Student-teacher ratio and average class size

Source: Education at a Glance

When comparing Rwanda and the OECD as benchmarks for quality education, it is evident that Rwanda has a higher pupil-teacher ratio in primary schools, with 44 more pupils per teacher than the OECD average. This indicates that teachers in Rwanda may face challenges in providing quality education to a large number of students during class sessions, as they may struggle to effectively monitor and assess each child's progress in developing literacy and numeracy skills. As a result, the prevalence of learning poverty in Rwanda is relatively high.

Reflections on the current situation

Rwanda is ranked among the top countries in achieving education for all, however, this great achievement has done serious issues become learning outcomes (what learners gain in schooling). Government effort for achieving education for all was not simultaneously balanced with an increase in school infrastructure and an effective number of trained teachers which results in a lack of quality education.

The current figures show how education is suffering in achieving quality education the overall purpose of the education sector was to promote access to quality, equitable and effective education for all Rwandans. Consistently, one of the objectives of Economic Development Poverty Reduction Strategies (EDPRS) for education was to improve and increase equity in education at all levels. Nevertheless, equitable distribution of the available resources in all levels of schools across the country remains an unfinished business.

The table presents examples of various resource distributions at different levels of education in Rwanda.

School level	Pupil-teacher ratio	Pupil-qualified teacher ratio	Pupil-trained teacher ratio	Pupil-classroom ratio			Pupil-desk ratio			Pupil-textbook ratio	Pupil-computer ratio	Pupil-toilet ratio
				1	2	3	1	2	3			
Nursery	36:1	40:1	71:1	62	61	36	2	3	2	13:1		25:1
Primary	57:1	58:1	60:1	82	75	32	5	5	2	5:1	10:1	52:1

Figure 6. Resource distribution in different levels of education in Rwanda

Source: MINEDUC 2019

1: Public schools 2: Government-aided schools 3: Private schools

Table 1 shows the data concerning the distribution of resources (Human & Material) as part of input factors provided in different Rwandan education levels namely: nursery, primary.

Considering all indicators presented in Table 1, the primary school level marks the highest records among others. As a matter of concern, the pupil-teacher ratio is 57:1, the pupil-qualified teacher ratio 58:1, pupil-trained teacher ratio 60:1, but this is slightly lesser than 71:1 in nursery schools, pupil-classroom ratio 82:1 in public schools, the pupil-desk ratio 5:1 in public government-aided primary schools, pupil-textbook ratio 5:1 also this indicator is lesser than 13:1 in nursery schools, pupil-computer ratio 10:1, then pupil-toilet ratio 52:1. This data is running against Post-2015 agendas and education for all (EFA) which recommend governments to ensure that all learners are taught by qualified, professionally trained teacher.

This data indicates an inadequate number of required resources in primary and nursery schools like qualified & trained teachers, classrooms, desks, textbooks, computers and toilets, a fact which indicates inequitable distribution of resources in different educational levels. Consistently, MINEDUC (2020) claims a gap of 22,000 classrooms and 31,000 latrines, a challenge which enforces overcrowding as well as long-distance covered by students to reach schools.

Literacy and numeracy remain at 45.3% and 32.9% in P2 literacy and numeracy respectively while 44.1% and 38.3% in P5 literacy and numeracy in 2021. Regarding the overall concern of learning outcomes, Rwanda scored 358 on a scale out of 300 and 625 minimum and maximum scale respectively in the global assessment of learning for the human capital project. The additional concern could be the evidence suggested by the World Bank substantiating that among the other countries categorized in the same income, Rwanda falls back in the progress of providing quality education. While teachers are still being paid salaries far less than purchasing power parity [24].

Figure 7. The proportion of children who can read a simple text, as of 28 February 2022

Source [25]

As per the report, a considerable number of developing nations, Rwanda included, exhibit a score of less than 35% in terms of children's ability to read a basic text by the age of 10. This implies that a majority, i.e., over 65%, of children enrolled in schools are currently grappling with learning poverty. Despite a significant enrollment rate in schools, learning outcomes remain poor, while global transformations necessitate individuals with skills for survival. The attainment of a successful future generation is contingent upon the provision of fundamental skills to our children, which serve as the foundation for further academic pursuits and the world of work. Failure to provide such skills would impede progress towards this goal.

Consequently, the quality of education in Rwanda presents several flaws, with inadequate ability to effectively compete in the national and international market for the concerned graduates. Economically, fail achievement of growing to a middle-income country that has been planned by 2020 the increase in unemployment rate, and citizen's well-being remain unanswered issues.

Looking forward to the future

Drawing on the theoretical framework of globalization and its potential impact on education, this study examines the various challenges associated with learning poverty in primary schools in Rwanda, while also exploring potential remedies to address this issue. The term "globalization" is a historical process, the result of human innovation and technological progress. The term sometimes also refers to the movement of people (labour) and knowledge (technology) across international borders. It pertains to a complex economic and social phenomenon that emerged during the early 1980s. This phenomenon encompasses a range of interconnected economic, political cultural and environmental factors [26].

The change in the nature of the jobs market is driven by the massive development in technology. It is erasing more and low skills jobs due to automation. These same jobs were used to supply many low-skill workers with money by which they could survive. Technology is presenting more possibilities to explore the world. Yet, it's placing a threat on low skilled workers thus only quality education and lifelong learning would save a high portion of people in the world out of poverty [8]. The lack of basic skills and/or a minimum standard of education significantly decreases the chances for

an individual to succeed in the labour market, and, generally, in life. Moreover, the risk of being permanently excluded from the labour market is highest among poorly educated individuals (Solga, 2006) cited in [5].

To effectuate this transformation, the government should prioritize education as a fundamental objective, necessitating significant investment of resources. The execution of the task must be characterized by a sense of accountability and precision and must culminate in the acquisition of knowledge through the process of education. The objectives such as providing high-quality education and addressing educational disadvantaged groups should be emphasized in all facets of education. Although the expense may be substantial, the results are significant. The potential benefits of investing in education may not be immediately realized, however, when coupled with high-quality education, it can yield a highly skilled human capital that is equipped to accelerate the development of a nation.

The global environment for education is also changing. One set of changes is demographic within which lower fertility rates are shifting population profiles from the very young populations typical of many low-income countries to “youth bulges” more typical of middle-income countries, increasingly concentrated in urban areas. Another set of changes is technological: incredible advances in information and communications technology (ICT) and other technologies are changing job profiles and skills demanded by labour markets, while also offering possibilities for accelerated learning and improved management of education systems [8].

Government should reinforce a merit-based teacher recruitment system, where only the most talented and motivated teachers can be selected, they can improve significantly the quality of education. Additionally, teachers should get more integrated into ongoing professional development to meet the need of students. Moreover, school inputs are as vital. Classrooms need to be equipped for learning through the presence of books and technology to support the learning experience and also through a simple, effective curriculum and structured pedagogic.

Teachers need to be valued and effective at what they do. As long as teachers are not receiving the value they deserve, it is hard to imagine a successful education system. The status of the teaching career matters a lot in the quality of delivery by teachers. Finish and Chinese teachers are effective in knowledge and skills delivery because the job comes with a prestigious status [27]& [28]. Rwanda should base on this good practice for increasing the status of the teaching profession through increased teachers’ salaries payment, and improved working conditions.

Teaching the fundamentals should be prioritized. Learning recovery efforts should focus on essential missed content and prioritize the most foundational skills and knowledge, particularly literacy and numeracy, that students need for learning within and across subjects and for more advanced learning in the future. This focus is especially important, given the dense and overreaching curricula implemented in the country, and it is essential to free teachers from the excessive burden of having to cover too much material. Learning programs should also help teachers to improve their teaching of foundational skills, notably through specific and practical training and teacher guides connected to well-designed student textbooks.

Psychosocial health and well-being should be developed. The pandemic has harmed the mental health and psychosocial well-being of both learners and teachers, compounding risks for those who are already marginalized. It is crucial to ensure that schools are safe and that children are healthy and protected from violence and can access basic services such as nutrition, counselling, water, sanitation, and hygiene services. Promoting children’s welfare is inherently of great value, and it also has the benefit of promoting learning: children learn best when they experience joy and a sense of belonging at school.

Learning levels should be assessed regularly. Measuring children’s current learning levels after their holidays return to school is essential, to help teachers target instruction in the classroom to each child’s starting point. This requires providing teachers with formative assessment tools that they can easily apply in the classroom. Regular system assessments and inspections with a focus on learning outcomes are also needed to guide system-level decisions on how to continue to reduce learning poverty.

Establishing national benchmarks for numeracy and literacy that are in line with the curriculum is crucial in promoting competent learners to the next level, while also providing adequate support for those who may be struggling to reach the desired level.

The efficacy of schools is depending upon the competence of their leadership. To this end, qualified head teachers must be recruited and trained to effectively manage schools. The accountability of head teachers, as well as the duties of teachers and the creation of a conducive learning environment for students, are all critical factors that impact school performance.

Conclusion

The analysis of increased primary students over the last 15 years has highlighted a concerning impact on education quality. This is primarily attributed to the discrepancy between the growing enrollment and the limited availability of learning infrastructure, tools, materials, and qualified teaching staff. Consequently, a learning poverty crisis has emerged within primary schools, accentuated by international reports from UNICEF, UNESCO, and the World Bank singling out Rwanda as a country needing to address this issue for the sake of achieving quality education.

To pave the way forward, an optimal education strategy revolves around early, strategic, and inclusive investments. The significance of acquiring foundational skills during early childhood cannot be overstated, as they serve as a cornerstone for lifelong learning. This shifts the traditional notion of education's start point to earlier stages. Smart investments that have proven to enhance learning outcomes are pivotal to achieving value for money in education. Prioritizing quality within these investments becomes paramount, with learning advancements serving as a critical benchmark.

Additionally, the vision of education for all demands an unwavering commitment to ensuring knowledge and skill acquisition for every student, regardless of their background or inherent abilities. To transform this vision into reality, robust systems must be established, capable of consistently delivering impactful learning experiences to countless students daily. Achieving successful education reforms necessitates well-crafted policies, steadfast political dedication, and adept implementation.

Acknowledging the challenges that arise in this journey is essential. Allocating resources optimally and translating increased investments into tangible knowledge gains pose ongoing dilemmas. Overcoming these obstacles requires a comprehensive approach that intervenes across all levels of the education system. By addressing the crisis of learning poverty head-on, the path towards fostering an effective and productive skilled human capital base for the nation becomes clear. In doing so, Rwanda can not only eliminate learning poverty but also cultivate a future defined by empowered individuals and enhanced national growth.

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